

POST EXPEDITION REPORT

Field Expedition La Réunion Island 2024, France

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DISCLAIMER

The ideas and opinions expressed in this report are the authors alone. They do not necessarily reflect the opinions or ideas of the funding agencies, employers, or corporate sponsors.

Submitted by

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ABSTRACT

This mission focused on exploring the ecological and biogeochemical dynamics of La Réunion's unique peatlands and tropical montane ecosystems. Key activities included coring and geochemical sampling at the Mare au Thym and Plaine des Palmistes, complemented by *Sphagnum* patch sampling and exploratory studies at Piton Cabri. Rain collectors were installed at Maïdo and STAFOR as part of the PLUIESTIQUE project to analyze atmospheric deposition. These efforts aim to deepen our understanding of carbon storage, nitrogen cycles, and particle transport in volcanic environments. Findings contribute to global studies on tropical peatland resilience and ecosystem processes.

RESUME

Cette mission a exploré les dynamiques écologiques et biogéochimiques des tourbières et écosystèmes tropicaux montagnards uniques de La Réunion. Les activités principales incluait des carottages et échantillonnages géochimiques à la Mare au Thym et à la Plaine des Palmistes, ainsi que des prélèvements dans des patches de Sphaignes et des études exploratoires au Piton Cabri. Des collecteurs de pluie ont été installés au Maïdo et à la STAFOR dans le cadre du projet PLUIESTIQUE pour analyser les dépôts atmosphériques. Ces travaux visent à mieux comprendre le stockage du carbone, les cycles de l'azote et le transport des particules dans ces environnements volcaniques, contribuant aux recherches mondiales sur la résilience des tourbières tropicales.

GENERAL INFORMATION

Contact information

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Travel, accommodation and logistics

1. Travel

Participants arrived in La Réunion from various locations, and vehicles were rented through the **CNRS system with Hertz** at the airport to facilitate travel to field sites. This arrangement ensured smooth logistics for accessing diverse and often remote study areas.

2. Accommodation

Accommodation was organized in **Airbnbs** located near field sites, offering flexibility and convenience for the team's activities. However, for the nights of **2 and 3 September 2024**, the team stayed at the **OPAR-Maïdo station** to accommodate specific fieldwork in this region.

3. Arrivals and Departures

The following table summarizes the arrival and departure dates for the team members:

Name	Role	Date of Departure (Origin)	Date of Arrival (La Réunion)	Date of Departure (La Réunion)
David Beilman	Researcher, USA PeatCReu24, Carbon Islands	31 August 2024	1 September 2024	16 September 2024
Sophia Hansson	Researcher, France	27 August 2024	28 August 2024	11 September 2024

Name	Role	Date of Departure (Origin)	Date of Arrival (La Réunion)	Date of Departure (La Réunion)
	Carbon Islands, PluieStique			
Romain Darnajoux	Researcher, France VanaPeat	31 August 2024	1 September 2024	6 September 2024
Gaël Le Roux	Researcher, France PeatCReu24, Carbon Islands, VanaPeat, PluieStique	27 August 2024	28 August 2024	11 September 2024
Dirk Sachse	Researcher, Germany PeatCReu24	4 September 2024	4 September 2024	10 September 2024
Michelle McKeown	Researcher, Ireland PeatCReu24	6 September 2024	6 September 2024	16 September 2024

1.1. Funding and Project Origins

This mission was supported by a combination of national and international research projects, highlighting the collaborative and interdisciplinary nature of the work. Key funding sources and project affiliations include:

- **TNA Atmo-Access (PeatCReu24):** Funded through the Atmo-Access TransNational Access program through the OPAR National facility, this project focuses on understanding the long-term sensitivity and resilience of montane peatlands, with a comparative analysis of environmental archives between La Réunion and Hawai'i.
- **Carbon Islands (EC2CO, CNRS):** This project investigates the biogeochemical impact of *Sphagnum* mosses on the hydrology and carbon dynamics of La Réunion's catchments.
- **VanaPeat (Marie Curie Fellowship):** Aims to unravel the nitrogen dynamics in tropical cloud forests and peatlands.
- **PluieStique (MITI, CNRS):** Focused on studying the hydrological and chemical processes linked to rainfall in tropical montane environments.
- **Atlas des Tourbières de France (WWF, Editions Biotope):** A project that highlights the importance of La Réunion's peatlands in a dedicated chapter on overseas territories.

1.2. Introduction

Peatlands are globally significant ecosystems due to their capacity for long-term carbon storage, water regulation, and biodiversity conservation. In tropical regions, these ecosystems are particularly unique, with specific dynamics shaped by local climatic and geological conditions. On volcanic islands like La Réunion, peatlands develop in areas where ***Sphagnum* mosses**, known as foundational, architectural, and engineering species, accumulate organic matter and profoundly transform recently formed volcanic soils.

The presence of such ecosystems on La Réunion has resulted in highly distinctive forest and grassland landscapes. To understand their ancient and current roles, the mission focused on:

- Investigating the **ecological dynamics of *Sphagnum* mosses**, both past and present.
- Analyzing the **Critical Zone's function** during major climatic periods, including the Last Glacial Maximum and the Holocene.
- Assessing current **biogeochemical exports** to surrounding watersheds.

The mission continues the work initiated during a **2021 campaign** (Margenat and Le Roux, 2023), where upper peat profiles were sampled, and a core over **25,000 years old** was retrieved at the Mare au Thym. This highlighted the exceptional value of La Réunion's peatlands as environmental archives for the Indian Ocean region. The 2024 campaign expanded these investigations to new sites with a focus on **long peat cores** and complementary surface sampling for geochemical studies.

1.3. State of the Art

1. Tropical Peatlands in the Global Context

Tropical peatlands differ significantly from their temperate counterparts. They are characterized by rapid accumulation rates, higher decomposition potentials, and strong interactions with local hydrology. Research in tropical montane island regions remains sparse, making islands like La Réunion (Straka, 1960) valuable case studies.

2. Role of *Sphagnum* Mosses

Sphagnum mosses are critical to peat formation due to their ability to:

- Accumulate organic matter at rates exceeding decomposition.
- Lower pH levels, creating acidic environments that slow microbial activity.
- Influence water retention and nutrient dynamics in peatlands. Recent studies emphasize their role as **key biogeochemical modulators** and their potential impact on watershed nutrient fluxes.

3. Tropical Peatland Archives

Peatlands serve as natural archives, preserving information about past climates, vegetation, and ecosystem dynamics. The Mare au Thym peat core revealed environmental changes over the past 25,000 years, underlining the potential of La Réunion's peatlands to reconstruct paleoenvironmental conditions in the Indian Ocean basin.

4. Current Research Gaps

Despite advances in understanding tropical peatlands, significant gaps remain:

- Limited knowledge of **biogeochemical cycling** in tropical montane peatlands.
- Few comparative studies on the interactions between **peat-forming vegetation** and volcanic substrates.
- A lack of high-resolution data on **historical and contemporary hydrological dynamics** in volcanic islands.

This campaign addressed these gaps by combining sediment coring, geochemical flux monitoring, and vegetation sampling to link past and present ecological processes.

1.4. Sampling Sites and Locations

Figure 1: location of the peatlands (REU 21-5: Cap Anglais sampled in 2021, REU21-4: Mare au Thym sampled in 2021 and 2024, REU24-PAN: studied in 2021 and 2024, REU24-CAB: Piton Cabri explored in 2024, REU21-6: Savane Cimetièrre Zone des Mares cored in 2021). Background map from (Leroux et al., n.d.)

The sampling campaign was conducted across several key locations on La Réunion, targeting ecosystems that reflect the unique interactions between vegetation, hydrology, and volcanic substrates. The primary focus was on two peatland sites, complemented by additional sampling in *Sphagnum* patches and exploratory locations.

Mare au Thym (1,536 m a.s.l.)

Located in the **Plaine des Marsouins**, this high-altitude peatland represents one of La Réunion's most significant environmental archives. Previous studies revealed a peat core exceeding **25,000 years** in age. During this mission, depth surveys were conducted to assess peat stratigraphy, identify the transition to sediment, and evaluate the onset of turfigenesis. Additionally, the surrounding soils were mapped for chemical composition using portable XRF analysis. Twelve surface *Sphagnum* samples were collected to investigate testate amoebae assemblage patterns across micro-topographical gradients (lawns, hummocks, hollows), along with pH and conductivity of groundwater when encountered.

Plaine des Palmistes (890 m a.s.l.):

Situated at a lower altitude, this site exhibits contrasting peat dynamics. On one side of the road, the peat layer was limited to 50 cm, resting directly on a basaltic bedrock. Across the road, peat accumulation reached 90 cm, providing a deeper sampling opportunity. This duality illustrates how substrate and hydrology influence peat formation processes. Eight surface *Sphagnum* samples were collected to investigate testate amoebae assemblage patterns following the same method as carried out in Mare au Thym.

1. Survey on the 2021 Sampling Side

In the area previously sampled in 2021, David Beilman and Michelle McKeown conducted an in-depth survey 0-43cm – monolith core using two half pipes and a bread knife

40-90cm – Russian core drive from coring hole 10cm away from monolith core. Felt like it bottomed out on basalt bedrock. But bottom ~10cm missing owing to Russian corer design and the bullet head bottom.

A second Russian core drive 10cm from the first Russian drive was taken to get a basal sample for 14C. y. a **90 cm peat core** was collected (S 21.116864, E 055.649414).

2. Survey on the other side of the road (-21.119225, 55.643511)

This area shows significantly higher organic matter accumulation, offering a useful contrast to the previously surveyed zone. This sampling will allow:

- The study of peat stratigraphy.
- A better understanding of local conditions favoring greater organic matter accumulation.

Figure 2: a) wet vegetation and mosses including *Sphagnum* on the edge of a volcanic slab b) wet pool accumulating more than 70cm of organic rich sediment

2. Additional locations included:

- ***Sphagnum* patches in forested areas**, notably along the **Sentier Mollaret** and the **Sentier du Gol**, where vegetation was sampled for geochemical analyses and biomarker studies.

Especially on Sentier du Gol, we took a monolith core with the pruning saw (rough cut) in sections 0-20cm, 20-30cm, 30-45cm, 45-75cm. The site seemed like it was mostly *Sphagnum tumidulum* but with a small patch of *Sphagnum strictum* (possibly ssp. *Pappeanum*) as well.

- **Piton Cabri**, an exploratory site where a preliminary assessment revealed **1.2 m of dark, high-quality peat**, though no samples were taken. Basal sample was taken and will be sent for ^{14}C .
- **Petite Mare**, a smaller wetland with **80 cm of peat**, adding to the diversity of sampling contexts. 29cm depth sample will be sent for ^{14}C .

This network of sites offers a comprehensive view of the diverse ecosystems on La Réunion, from deep peatland archives to surface patches dominated by *Sphagnum* mosses, and exploratory areas for future studies.

3. LIST OF SAMPLES

3.1. Mapping in Mare au Thym

Figure 3: aerial picture of Mare au Thym (credit D. Sachse)

XRF mapping and soil depth map

Figure 4: location of XRF measurements around Mare au Thym peatland (blue) and peat depth sampling (brown)

XRF mapping was performed by Sophia Hansson on surface soils using a Niton XLT3 Thermo handheld analyzer. This allowed for *in-situ* elemental analysis of the peatland edges at Mare au Thym. At the same time, she probed the soil depth at each measurement point to assess variations in surface accumulation and substrate composition. These combined measurements provide valuable insights into the geochemical properties of the peatland margins and their relationship with underlying soil structures.

Figure 5: handheld XRF measurements in Mare au Thym

Peat depth and peat coring

Bottom depth samples of peat profiles were collected and assessed for total peat depth to better understand accumulation dynamics. Additionally, two extra peat cores were extracted and transported back to Toulouse for further analysis. These cores are securely stored at -18°C to preserve their geochemical and biological integrity, ensuring accurate future investigations into past environmental conditions and peatland development.

Table 1: peat depth probe points in Mare au Thym

No	Longitude	Latitude	Elev	Field Code	depth_c m
1	55.54742	-21.0971	1555.335	W1	151
2	55.54723	-21.0972	1555.365	W2	161
3	55.54708	-21.0972	1555.323	W3	137
4	55.54689	-21.0972	1551.723	W4	61
5	55.54671	-21.0972	1553.926	W5	40
6	55.54764	-21.0972	1549.302	S1	90
				S2	55
7	55.54768	-21.0976	1545.762	S3	135
8	55.54765	-21.0978	1559.365	S4	180
9	55.54762	-21.0979	1565.721	S5	26.7
11	55.54756	-21.0969	1548.345	N1	39

12	55.54773	-21.0971	1553.15	E1	56
13	55.54794	-21.0971	1560.054	E2	34
14	55.54812	-21.0971	1563.022	E3	40
15	55.54826	-21.0971	1552.899	E4	12.7
16	55.54755	-21.0972	1551.447	SW1	47
17	55.54745	-21.0976	1550.995	SW2	86
18	55.54721	-21.0977	1552.637	SW3	64
19	55.54708	-21.0979	1547.062	SW4	91
21	55.54733	-21.097	1553.76	SE1	160
22	55.54728	-21.0972	1552.771	SE2	150
23	55.54709	-21.0972	1552.993	SE3	171

The peat depth at Mare au Thym appears to be heterogeneously distributed, likely influenced by lava tubes or subsurface cavities, similar to the holes observed along the edges of the peatland, suggesting that subsurface volcanic features play a role in peat accumulation and retention.

Peat cores:

REU24A – two drives with Russian corer roughly 0-50 and 50-100

REU24B – overlapping section roughly 25-75

REU24A/REU24B raised at 21.097165S, 055.547537 (PON0039)

REU24C – two drives with Russian corer raised at 21.097115S, 055.547433E (PON0037)

REU24D/REU24E raised at 21.097043S, 055.547526E (PON0038)

Core taken from small pond, 0-50 drive b the side of the pond in *Sphagnum* area. A basal sample was removed at ~25cm (see photo). Core raised at 21.098708S, 055.546930E (PON0045)

Core taken from 'Center area' – we walked into region identified by Kriging surface to have deeper peat. Core 'Centre 1' raised at 21.097322S, 05.547771E (PON0046)

Figure 6: REU 4-2024 A

Figure 7: REU 4-2024 B (25-75) : overlap of core REU4 2024

Figure 8: REU 4 - 2024 C

Figure 9: REU 4-2024-D

Figure 10: REU 4 2024 25-75 E

Figure 11: REU 4 2024 small pond

Water Samples

Around 15 samples of river, pond and squeezed water samples were collected too for stable isotope exploration and major ion determination with a focus on Mare au Thym.

Table 2: water samples

Name	Location or type of sample
mot0	Mare au Thym squeezed sphag
mot1	Mare au Thym inlet
mot2	Mare au Thym edge water
mot3	Mare au Thym lave tube
mot4	Mare au Thym small pond
mot5	Mare au Thym itself
mol squeeze	Mollaret Squeezed sphag water
plainepalmistes L	Plaine des Palmistes pond
Gol river	Sentier du Gol river
Molbridge	Mollaret bridge river
Molbridge bis	Mollaret bridge river
Gol Squeeze	Sentier du Gold squeezed sphag
Piton Cabri bottle	Piton Cabri
Piton Cabri squeezed water	Piton Cabri squeezed sphag
Plaine des Fougères sq sphag	Plaine des Fougères squeezed sphag
Plaine des Fougères	Plaine des Fougères water

The hydrology of Mare au Thym appears to be characterized by slow or negligible water table recharge, with previously sampled areas remaining dry over multiple days, indicating low water retention and limited groundwater connectivity in the peatland. Water table was reached at only two locations and was measured at 30 cm and 52 cm below the ground surface and pH was 4.1-4.2. Small sampling holes were dug over 80 cm depth to reach the water table at 10 further locations and left recharge, but no water collected. Holes were subsequently refilled with peat and *Sphagnum*.

pH values at Mare Au Thym: 4.1-4.2, n = 2

4. Vegetation surface sampling

4.1. Molecular markers

Vegetation sampling was also conducted to investigate biomolecular proxies of plant-derived organic matter preserved in the peat cores. These samples will be analyzed to identify molecular markers that can provide insights into past vegetation dynamics and environmental conditions.

Table 3: location and type of vegetation samples (Dirk Sachse)

location	altitude	type	species
-21.16061, 55.55673	1727	water	
-21.09700, 55.54747	1538	plant	<i>Hubertia ambavilla</i>
-21.09701, 55.54750	1538	plant	
-21.09705, 55.54747	1538	plant	<i>Juncus effusus (sedge)</i>
-21.09708, 55.54753	1538	plant	<i>Polytrichum subpilosum Moss</i>
-21.09709, 55.54758	1538	plant	<i>Sphagnum</i>
-21.09701, 55.54753	1538	plant	<i>Cyperaceae (sedge)</i>
-21.09722, 55.54800	1538	plant	<i>Erica</i>
-21.09722, 55.54800	1538	plant	<i>Hubertia ambavilla</i>
-21.09722, 55.54800	1538	plant	<i>Juncus effusus</i>
-21.09722, 55.54800	1538	plant	<i>Sphagnum sp.</i>
-21.09722, 55.54800	1538	plant	<i>Polytrichum subpilosum</i>
-21.09722, 55.54800	1538	plant	<i>Cyperaceae</i>
-21.09726, 55.54746	1535	plant	<i>Juncus effusus</i>
-21.09726, 55.54746	1535	plant	<i>Asteraceae</i>
-21.09726, 55.54746	1535	plant	<i>Sphagnum</i>
-21.09726, 55.54746	1535	plant	<i>Polytrichum subpilosum</i>
-21.09726, 55.54746	1535	plant	<i>Erica</i>

Additional samples from Plaine des Palmistes (Pandanaies) :

Collected plant leaf tissue samples (n=14):

Lycopodiella cernua

Sphagnum sp.

Psidium cattleianum

Stoebe passerinoides (or *Syzygium pasiunensis*) – to be confirmed in the lab

Machaerina iridifolia

Osmunda regalis

Dicranopteris linearis

Cordyline mauritiana

Cyperaceae (unk.)

Juncus effusus

Erica reunionensis

Hubertia tomentosa

Pandanus montanus

Sticherus flagellaris

4.2. Thecamoebian biodiversity

Lab_code	Site Name	Transect #	Sample #	Lat S	Long E	GPS code	Habitat	Micro-habitat	Depth to water table (cm)	pH (water)	Mositure (%)	Bulk density (g/cm3)
X24_LR_P_T1_S1	Pandanaies	1	1	21.116847	055.649314	PON0050	Peatland	Sphagnum Lawn	No water reached	No water reached	NA	NA
X24_LR_P_T1_S2	Pandanaies	1	2	21.116891	055.64933	PON0051	Peatland	Sphagnum Lawn	5	4.94	NA	NA
X24_LR_P_T1_S3	Pandanaies	1	3	21.11693	055.649368	PON0052	Peatland	Sphagnum hummock	10.5	5.33	NA	NA
X24_LR_P_T1_S4	Pandanaies	1	4	21.116947	055.649403	PON0054	Peatland	Sphagnum hummock	7.5	4.7	NA	NA
X24_LR_P_T1_S5	Pandanaies	1	5	21.116599	055.648869	PON0083	Peatland	Lawn	NA	NA	93.2038835	0.7
X24_LR_P_T1_S6	Pandanaies	1	6	21.116459	055.648869	PON0085	Peatland	Pool	12	6.1	93.27731092	0.8
X24_LR_P_T1_S7	Pandanaies	1	7	21.116551	055.648847	PON0086	Peatland	Small Sphagnum hummock	NA	NA	85.29411765	0.5
X24_LR_P_T1_S8	Pandanaies	1	8	21.116523	055.648470	PON0088	Peatland	Sphagnum lawn	14	5.6	95.83333333	0.4
X24_LR_M_T1_S1	Mare Au Thym	1	1	21.097282	055.547574	PON0079	Peatland	Sphagnum Lawn	NA	NA	92.53731343	0.5
X24_LR_M_T1_S2	Mare Au Thym	1	2	21.097280	055.547537	PON0080	Peatland	Sphagnum hummock	NA	NA	90.90909091	0.5
X24_LR_M_T1_S3	Mare Au Thym	1	3	21.09731	055.547620	PON0081	Peatland	Sphagnum hallow	NA	NA	85.71428571	0.4
X24_LR_M_T1_S4	Mare Au Thym	1	4	21.097303	055.547626	PON0082	Peatland	Sphagnum hummock	NA	NA	86.66666667	0.4
X24_LR_M_T2_S1	Mare Au Thym	2	1			PON0067	Peatland	Sphagnum lawn	NA	NA	87.23404255	0.6
X24_LR_M_T2_S2	Mare Au Thym	2	2			PON0068	Peatland	Sphagnum lawn	NA	NA	85.91549296	1
X24_LR_M_T2_S3	Mare Au Thym	2	3			PON0069	Peatland	Sphagnum hummock	NA	NA	85.18518519	0.4
X24_LR_M_T2_S4	Mare Au Thym	2	4			PON0070	Peatland	Sphagnum lawn	NA	NA	83.01886792	0.9
X24_LR_M_T2_S5	Mare Au Thym	2	5			PON0071	Peatland	Small Sphagnum hummock	NA	NA	85.41666667	0.7
X24_LR_M_T2_S6	Mare Au Thym	2	6			PON0072	Peatland	Sphagnum lawn	NA	NA	85.9375	0.9
X24_LR_M_T2_S7	Mare Au Thym	2	7			PON0073	Peatland	Small Sphagnum hummock	NA	NA	87.75510204	0.6
X24_LR_M_T2_S8	Mare Au Thym	2	8			PON0074	Peatland	Sphagnum hummock	NA	NA	87.83783784	0.9
X24_LR_M_T2_S9	Mare Au Thym	2	9			PON0075	Peatland	Sphagnum hallow	NA	NA	87.5	0.9
X24_LR_M_T2_S10	Mare Au Thym	2	10			PON0076	Peatland	Sphagnum hallow	30	4.1	96	0.4
X24_LR_M_T2_S11	Mare Au Thym	2	11			PON0077	Peatland	Sphagnum lawn	52	4.2	94	0.3
X24_LR_M_T2_S12	Mare Au Thym	2	12			PON0078	Peatland	Sphagnum hummock	NA	NA	95.65217391	0.2
X24_LR_CAB_S1	Foewr de la Plaine c	Not collect	S1	21.161778	055.653835	PON0055	Forest with S	Sphagnum matt on tree	NA	NA	NA	NA
X24_LR_CAB_S2	Foewr de la Plaine c	Not collect	S2	21.161925	055.65347	PON0057	Forest with S	Wet Sphagnum sample taker	NA	NA	NA	NA
X24_LR_CAB_S3	Foewr de la Plaine c	Not collect	S3	21.161925	055.65347	PON0057	Forest with S	Drier Sphagnum 1.2 m above	NA	NA	NA	NA
X24_LR_CAB_S4	Foewr de la Plaine c	Not collect	S4	21.161783	055.652678	PON0058	Forest with Sphagnum matt		18	5.5	NA	NA
X24_LR_CAB_S5	Foewr de la Plaine c	Not collect	S5	21.161783	055.652678	PON0058	Forest with Sphagnum matt		NA	NA	NA	NA
X24_LR_CAB_S6	Foewr de la Plaine c	Not collect	S6	21.161725	055.654074	PON0059	Forest besid	Near dry stream	NA	NA	NA	NA
X24_LR_CAB_S7	Foewr de la Plaine c	Not collect	S7	21.161725	055.654074	PON0059	Forest overh	anging from seep	NA	NA	NA	NA
X24_LR_PM	Petite Mare	T1	S1	21.063624	055.556679	PON0062	Peatland (?)	Juncus effusus dominated wi	14	5.2	NA	NA
X24_LR_PM	Petite Mare	T1	S2	21.063515	055.55667	PON0063	Peatland (?)	ephemeral?	10	5.1	NA	NA
X24_LR_F	Foret des Fougeres	N/A	S1	20.982508	055.519742	PON0048	Forest	sample taken from epiphyte c	NA	NA	NA	NA
X24_LR_F	Foret des Fougeres	N/A	S2	20.982508	055.519742		Forest	Composite bryophyte	NA	NA	NA	NA
X24_LR_F	Foret des Fougeres	N/A	S3	20.982508	055.519742		Forest	Composite bryophyte	NA	NA	NA	NA
X24_LR_F	Foret des Fougeres	N/A	S4	20.982508	055.519742		Forest	Composite bryophyte	NA	NA	NA	NA
X24_LR_F	Foret des Fougeres	N/A	S5	20.982508	055.519742		Forest	Composite soil & moss	NA	NA	NA	NA

4.3. Moss sampling (Vanapeat project)

Bag	Site	Sub-site	Détails	Content	Mass	Date
150 1	1_Sentier du Gol	0	Entrée du chemin	Pseudoscleropodium sp.	2g	03/09/2024
150 2	1_Sentier du Gol	1	Lunch break area	Peltigera bipartite, Sphagnum sp., Dicranaceae sp.	22g	03/09/2024
150 3	1_Sentier du Gol	2	Milieux du sentier	Sphagnum sp., Thuidium sp., Hypnum sp., Dicranoloma billiarderi	20g	03/09/2024
150 4	1_Sentier du Gol	3	Au niveau du gros patch de Sphagnum	Sphagnum, Peltigera bipartite, Hypnaceae	10g	03/09/2024
150 5	1_Sentier du Gol	4	Sur le chemin	Pseudoscleropodium sp.	4g	03/09/2024
150 6	2_Plaines des Cafres	0		Sticta sp.	2g	04/09/2024
150 7	2_Plaines des Cafres	1		Hepatique, Peltigera bipartite	2g	04/09/2024
150 8	2_Plaines des Cafres	2		Hepatiques	1g	04/09/2024
150 9	2_Plaines des Cafres	1	Haut du site Piton tortu Piton bleu	Sphagnum, Peltigera bipartite, Thuidium sp.	5g	04/09/2024
151 0	2_Plaines des Cafres	2	Avoune Piton bleu	Dicranoloma, Peltigera bipartite	8g	04/09/2024
151 1	2_Plaines des Cafres	2	Avoune Piton bleu	Sphagnum	5g	04/09/2024
151 2	2_Plaines des Cafres	3		Pseudoscleropodium, Hepatic	12g	04/09/2024
151 3	2_Plaines des Cafres	4	Collecté à la sortie sur le retour	Sphagnum, Hypnaceae	5g	04/09/2024
151 4	3_Mare au Thym	0	Bord de route sous bosquet proche parking	Hypnum	9g	06/09/2024
151 5	3_Mare au Thym	1a	Canopée ouverte	Pseudoscleropodium, Hypnum	15g	06/09/2024
151 6	3_Mare au Thym	1b	Canopée fermée	Sphagnum	10g	06/09/2024
151 7	3_Mare au Thym	1c	Sur le chemin vers tourbière	Hypnum	8g	06/09/2024
151 8	3_Mare au Thym	2a	Canopée fermée dans tourbière	Hypnum	7g	06/09/2024
151 9	3_Mare au Thym	2b	Canopée ouverte dans tourbière	Hypnum	6g	06/09/2024
152 0	3_Mare au Thym	3	Avoune	Hypnum macrocarpum	3g	06/09/2024
152 1	3_Mare au Thym	3	Avoune	Plicanthus hirtelus	2.5g	06/09/2024
152 2	3_Mare au Thym	3	Avoune	Pleurozia gigantia	3g	06/09/2024
152 3	3_Mare au Thym	3	Avoune	Mastigophora	4g	06/09/2024
152 4	3_Mare au Thym	3	Avoune	Dicranoloma billardierei	4.5g	06/09/2024
152 4	3_Mare au Thym	3	Avoune	Sphagnum sp. (phenotype vert & rouge)	3g	06/09/2024
152 5	4_Plaines des fougères	2	GPS2	Plicanthus hirtelus	2g	09/09/2024
152 6	4_Plaines des fougères	1	GPS1	Bazzania decrescens	2g	09/09/2024
152 7	4_Plaines des fougères	2	GPS2	Sphagnum sp.	2g	09/09/2024
152 8	4_Plaines des fougères	1	GPS1	Mastigophora	2g	09/09/2024
152 9	4_Plaines des fougères	2	GPS2	Dicranoloma	2g	09/09/2024
153 0	4_Plaines des fougères	1	GPS1	Polytrichum	2g	09/09/2024
153 1	4_Plaines des fougères	1	GPS1	Ectropothecium	2g	09/09/2024

5. Plaine des Palmistes

At Plaine des Palmistes, the peatland under the *Pandanus* forest was explored on both sides of the road. This site is particularly interesting due to the removal of part of the peat for the construction of an electric power line.

The stream flowing over the volcanic rock slab already hosts *Sphagnum* mosses, providing an opportunity to study their formation by analogy, and even the potential development of peat directly on a volcanic substrate.

On the left side of the road (going downhill), several pools contain between 1 to 1.5 meters of peat. Water table was variable across the site and was encountered at five locations (5 cm, 10.5 cm, 7.5 cm, 12 cm, and 14 cm below the surface), the other four locations ground water was not reached due to bedrock. pH of water was between 4.7 and 6.1. On the right side of the road, where a previous core sample was taken, the peat layer is much thinner (50cm).

pH values in Plaine des Palmistes : 4.7-6.1, n = 5

6. Exploration of other sites

Sentier du Pito Textor (-21.165856, 55.627689): no peat in a deep small crater

Piton Cabri peatland: 1.2m of nice dark peat

Forêt Bebour-Belouve:

Petite Mare . ~80cm peat

From REU24 trip, three basal peat samples were collected:

1. Pandanaies, 89-90cm
2. Piton Cabris, 99-100cm
3. Petit Mare 28-29cm

Figure 12: view from Cabri peatland

Figure 13: inside a crater along the trail to Piton Textor (no peat)

Figure 14 La petite Mare

7. Installation of Rain collectors for MITI PluieStique project

1. A high-volume Palmex RS2 collector was installed at 2,200 m a.s.l. inside the OPAR-Maïdo National Facility, in colocation with IR-ACTRIS and IR-ICOS labelled instruments, useful for further interpretation works. In the framework of Pluiestique CNRS MITI project, OPAR-Maïdo National Facility is strongly related to OZC-R Forest station, second place used for Palmex collector installation. The Palmex RS2 collector. This system features a large funnel (160 mm diameter) directing rainwater into a 10 L collection container. Its robust design, including a splash guard and bird deterrent, ensures effective collection even under extreme weather conditions such as cyclones.

Figure 15:rain collector at OPAR-Maïdo observatory

2. STAFOR Station (Saint-Philippe):

A smaller Palmex RS1 collector was installed at a lower altitude (~100 m a.s.l.) in a forested area (OZC-R Forest station).. With a 135 mm funnel and a 3 L collection capacity, this collector is well-suited for areas with consistent, high precipitation rates.

Figure 16: Palmex rain collector at STAFOR

The collected rainwater in both sites will be analyzed for stable isotopes, trace elements, and particulate content, including microplastics. These samplers provide critical data on the transport and deposition of atmospheric particles in tropical montane ecosystems, aiding in long-term environmental monitoring and advancing our understanding of precipitation-related biogeochemical cycles.

8. PERSPECTIVES & FUTURE WORK

The collected samples will primarily be analyzed within the framework of several Master's theses, funded by the EC2CO and MITI projects, as well as by PhD student Xiannong Song, who is supported by a CSC fellowship. The research will focus on evaluating the carbon and nitrogen content of the samples, along with their biogeochemical dynamics in both forested and peatland environments.

Future field expeditions in 2025 will aim to identify and explore new potential peatland sites. Additionally, these trips will expand the scope of the study to include fog and water sampling, further enhancing our understanding of the hydrological and ecological processes influencing peatland formation and stability.

Team pictures:

Figure 17: field sampling in Mare au Thym. From left to right: Gaël Le Roux, Claudine Ah Peng, Nemo Fontanie, Sophia Hansson, David Beilman, Michelle McKeown, Romain Darnajoux, Dirk Sachse

Figure 18: In St Denis campus designing a robust rain collector platform. From left to right: David Combemale, François Rigaud Louise, Olivier Magand, Gaël Le Roux

Figure 19: At Maïdo observatory, From left to right: Olivier Magand, Sophia Hanssnn. Gaël Le Roux, Romain Darnajoux, Claudine Ah Peng, David Combemale, David Beilman

REFERENCES:

- Marie-Dominique Leroux, François Bonnardot, Stephason François Kotomangazafy, Abdoul-Oikil Said, Philippe Veerabadren, et al.. Régionalisation du changement climatique et développement de services climatiques dans le sud-ouest de l’océan Indien et ses territoires insulaires. METEO FRANCE. 2023. hal-03966983v7
- Margenat, H., Le Roux, G., 2023. POST EXPEDITION REPORT Field Expedition La Réunion Island, France ATMOPLASTIC Project. Zenodo.
- Straka, H., 1960. Erdkunde 14, 81–98.